

Shear-induced structural transitions in confined nematic soft interfaces

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Research on aqueous-interfaced liquid crystals (LCs) offered valuable outcomes leading to successful applications in sensing and actuation systems. The forward leap of the promising findings in stagnant LC systems will be achieved by the integration of LCs into automated flow systems. In fundamental microfluidics studies, the structural transitions of LC were induced by external fields; yet they were constrained to hard-interfaced flow confinements. In this study, we investigate the structural transitions in flowing nematic LCs confined in microfluidic channels with accessible, stable LC-aqueous soft interfaces. We demonstrate in experiments and in simulations that the applied bulk and interfacial shear significantly transform the director configurations of the nematic LC, due to the anchoring properties at the soft interface. The director profiles, as well as the topology, are influenced substantially by the mechanical stresses induced at the vicinity of the aqueous interfaces depending on the interfacial anchoring conditions, bulk nematic directors, and the direction of the shear. The experimental observations presented herein will guide the ongoing research on the flow of LC in microenvironments and are likely to open new horizons in the development of autonomous platforms including more complex LC phases.

Thermotropic liquid crystals (LCs) are complex oily state of matter which are employed in broad areas beyond display technologies including optics, electronics, sensing, and actuator technologies^{1–5}. Their wide usage originates from their unique elastic and optical properties that arise from their long-range orientational order while maintaining fluidic properties. These mesophase characteristics and their birefringence allow to explore the local molecular ordering through the use of simple polarized light microscopy in response to changes at the contacting interfaces of LCs^{1,6}. Significant number of recent studies that employ LCs in responsive systems focused on their interfacial phenomena in aqueous media, including the equilibrium and non-equilibrium interaction of LCs with the analytes in the aqueous phase (especially for sensing purposes), and the investigation of reactions to synthesize nanoscopic materials or small molecules, or their response to mechanical or chemical stresses at the interfaces of LCs^{2,3,7–11}. These successful results promise a variety of real-life applications based on exploiting the significant responsiveness of LCs even at low concentrations of the species—down to pM levels—and minimal mechanical stresses in the order of 1 Pa^{2,3,12}. Such responsive characteristics can further be transformed to answer recent technological needs; however, they were constrained to stagnant systems hindering their integration into automated systems for

sequential, high-throughput analysis. A substantial improvement on these systems will be achieved by integrating LCs into continuous, responsive flow systems.

LCs differ from isotropic liquids because of three key features, namely (i) orientational order of the LC molecules, eventually leading to the formation of topological defects^{13,14}, (ii) internal elasticity, and surface-induced ordering (also known as interfacial anchoring)^{13,14}. In stagnant systems, the director profile is in the equilibrium state defined by the minimization of the elastic free energy with the strain of LC¹⁵. Contrarily, in flowing LC systems, viscous forces compete with elastic forces in a confined medium that causes strain in the LC director profiles, creating new flow-induced states depending on the boundary conditions and topology of the confining geometry, which remain mostly unexplored^{16–18}. The flow of LCs is generally performed in microfluidic systems since their viscoelastic properties can be monitored at the micrometer scale while coupling elasticity and flow^{18–23}. The Ericksen number (Er) is the dimensionless quantity that defines the relevance of viscous with respect to elastic forces in flowing LC ($Er = \frac{\eta v_{LC} L}{K}$; where η is the viscosity, v_{LC} is the characteristic LC velocity, K is the elastic constant, L is the characteristic size)^{24,25}. In hard-walled microfluidics, the topological defect structures were revealed to be controlled via flow, and to be suitable for micro-cargo in “railed” transport systems^{20,21,26,27}. LC director configurations are velocity-dependent in microchannels in which it is

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possible to analyze their flow characteristics^{18–23,28}. The flow of LCs in microenvironments is categorized into three flow regimes. The “weak” flow regime ($Er \ll 1$) is characterized by the dominance of elastic forces over viscous effects, resulting in a low distortion of the director profile. The “strong” flow regime ($Er \gg 1$) occurs when viscous dissipation prevails over elasticity. The intermediate state is seen along with complex flow profiles at the medium flow regime resulting from the competing LC elasticity and viscous effects²⁰. Those regimes seen on Poiseuille flow are associated with director orientation-dependent Miesowicz viscosities¹. Further recent research also suggested that the structural transitions in the LC medium can be tuned by coupling external fields (thermal and electrical fields) to induce stable, useful nanoscopic structures in pure LCs^{26,27,29}. Such studies showed the versatility of the LC flow systems while also presenting opportunities for further improvements towards leading technologies.

Although promising, the recent research on LC microfluidics was inadequate to meet the need of accessible, free LC-aqueous interfaces for the exchange of external species due to the presence of solid confining interfaces of LCs. After promising studies on the hard interface and droplet-based microfluidics, the potential of constructing and tailoring an externally accessible and stable “soft” interface between LC and aqueous phases gained importance. Soft interface microfluidics were exemplified in past studies, firstly with coflowing isotropic fluids and immiscible liquid phases or gases^{30–33}. When the microchannel surfaces are priorly chemically modified, making distinct hydrophobic and hydrophilic flow paths inside microchannels, the multiphase flow is achieved with a stable interface that is defined by the Laplace pressure across the interface^{31–36}. In the earlier studies, the interface was shown to be stable when the pressure difference across two phase boundary varied between 3 to 80 mbar depending on the size scales ranging in the orders of 10 to 100 μm ^{33,35,36}. With simplest estimation, the interplay of surface anchoring energy ($\sim WL^2$, W being the surface anchoring energy $\sim 10^{-6} \text{N m}^{-1}$) and elastic deformations (KL , K being the elastic constant $\sim 10^{-11} \text{N}$) of LCs becomes crucial in a length scale of tens of micrometers ($L \sim 10 \mu\text{m}$). Hence, the optimal size of LC-based microfluidic devices can be estimated to be in the order of 10 μm . However, stabilization of the LC-aqueous soft interface and the maintained configurations of the LCs at such interfaces upon varying boundary and flow conditions is still in its infancy³⁷.

Within the context of this study, we seek to develop a microfluidic multiphase flow system where LC is in contact with aqueous, soft interfaces at predetermined locations to provide a forward leap toward their integration into advanced responsive systems. With pressure-driven flow, we investigated the independent roles of bulk and interfacial shear to the topology of the nematic director and the flow characteristics of the LCs as it defines the potential of the flowing LC-aqueous microfluidics in applications. The creation of stable soft LC-aqueous interfaces enables to track changes in LC phases both temporally and spatially due to the delicate response of the LCs to the chemical and mechanical changes in contacting aqueous interfaces.

Results

System of interest: Stable LC-aqueous phase soft-interfaced co-flow system

Nematic LC phase of 4-cyano-4'-pentylbiphenyl (5CB), which is immiscible with water phase, was used in the study (Fig. 1a). To form a stable interface of 5CB and water, we functionalized one side of the channel in the longitudinal direction with dimethyloctadecyl[3-(trimethoxysilyl)propyl]ammonium chloride (DMOAP) using flow-focusing for hydrophobicity whereas the rest remained uncoated and hydrophilic. Such a coating resulted in the preferential wetting of the DMOAP coated interface with 5CB when co-introduced into the channel with water at determined inlet pressures of 5CB (P_{5CB}) and aqueous (P_{Aq}) phase (Fig. 1b), thus forming a microfluidic flow system with a stable 5CB-water interface. We showed that either using unmodified bare glass or homogeneous DMOAP surfaces in microchannels, namely the absence of two distinct functionalities on channel surfaces, resulted in unsuccessful stabilization of LC-aqueous interface (Fig.

Fig. 1 | The system of interest. **a** Representative ordering symmetry of the nematic phase and molecular structure of 4-cyano-4'-pentylbiphenyl (5CB) molecule that maintains nematic phase at room temperature. **b** The brightfield microscopy image (x-y view) of 5CB-water co-flow system in a 500 μm wide channel (left) and polarized optical micrographs collected during weak flow showing the optical appearance of the 5CB maintained within channels with planar (middle) and homeotropic (right) 5CB-aqueous interface. The resulting cross-sectional LC director configurations are maintained in microchannels with (c) planar and (d) homeotropic aqueous interfaces. The blue and red circular symbols indicate the flow directions employed in experimental investigations corresponding to the indicated phases.

S2). The stability of virtual walls between flowing and contacting LC and aqueous phases have been evidenced in microfluidic channels³⁷. Such a channel is demonstrated in the representative brightfield and polarized light micrographs shown in Fig. 1b. The dark optical appearance confirmed the uniform perpendicular director field of 5CB to the imaging plane which results from (i) the homeotropic anchoring of 5CB at DMOAP coated interfaces and (ii) minimal distortion of the LC director field with flow. We also note that 5CB is known to maintain a planar anchoring at the interfaces of pure water, consistent with our observations in Fig. 1b showing the dark appearance of the LC-aqueous interface in the case of pure water (middle image). Thus, the nematic LC director profile within the channel is as the cross-sectional sketch shown in Fig. 1c. To maintain a homeotropic anchoring of 5CB at aqueous interface, we introduced 1 mM sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) surfactant solution, which is known to promote homeotropic anchoring³⁸. Such anchoring was confirmed with polarized optical microscopy which showed the bright appearance of the 5CB-aqueous interface after the introduction of the aqueous SDS solution (Fig. 1b), resulting in a configuration sketch as in Fig. 1d. Along with homeotropic anchoring, we observed that a stable two-phase flow in the microchannels persists even though the addition of SDS reduces the interfacial tension of the LC-aqueous interface^{39,40}.

Past studies of multiphase flow in homogenous microchannel interfaces showed that if Capillary number, the ratio of viscous forces to interfacial tension forces in multiphase microfluidics, ($Ca = \mu v_{LC} / \gamma$, where μ is the dynamic viscosity, v_{LC} is the characteristic velocity, and γ is the interfacial tension that is $\sim 30 \text{ mN/m}$ for 5CB-pure water interface⁴⁰) is smaller than 1, microchannel is in droplet generation mode⁴¹. In our study, we reached 5CB-water co-flow with an unruptured LC-aqueous interface

without observing droplet formation even at lower capillary numbers $Ca \sim O(10^{-5})$ for planar or homeotropic soft-interfaced 5CB flow, revealing the critical role of the contacting interfaces in interface stabilization. Resultantly, we were able to stabilize the two-phase system of the 5CB and aqueous phases from stagnant systems up to strong aligned flow configurations in both planar and homeotropic interfaces (evidenced in the next section). Such stabilization provided access to study the shear dependent flow of LCs while maintaining soft interfaces. In line with these characteristics, we observed that the interfaces were stable against applied pressure differences across the 5CB-aqueous interfaces introduced by maintaining unequal inlet pressures of aqueous phase and 5CB (i.e. when $P_{5CB} \neq P_{Aq.}$). The maximum pressure difference ($\Delta P_{max} = P_{Aq.} - P_{5CB}$) across the 5CB-aqueous interface was limited by the Laplace pressure $\Delta P_{max} = 2\gamma \sin(\frac{\pi}{2} - \theta_{5CB-Aq.})/d$ as demonstrated in the past literature, where d is the channel depth and $\theta_{5CB-Aq.}$ is the contact angle of the 5CB-water interface^{31,35}. We experimentally measured that $\Delta P_{max} = 36.3 \pm 4.8$ mbar ($n = 3$) for the channels with 14 μm depth and $\Delta P_{max} = 28.3 \pm 2.1$ mbar ($n = 3$) when $d = 20 \mu\text{m}$ for 5CB-pure water interfaces, and $\Delta P_{max} = 22.7 \pm 1.2$ mbar ($n = 3$) for 5CB-1 mM SDS interfaces. ($d = 20 \mu\text{m}$), consistently with the theoretical predictions^{31,35}.

The values obtained from analysis of the interface stabilization (i) allowed to operate our flow device in co-current and counter-current flow configurations, and (ii) provided us with the experimental opportunity to investigate the interfacial shear-dependent alignment of the LCs at the aqueous interfaces under varying shear conditions for planar and homeotropic anchoring conditions. Thus, in the following sections, we investigate the structural and topological properties of the nematic 5CB under varying bulk and interfacial shear, and consider both planar and homeotropic soft interfaces. In these studies, we used two distinct bulk flows of nematic 5CB that correspond to the weak flow or the strong flow within the bulk that are characterized by the minimal and significant shear aligned states, respectively. Because we were particularly interested in the influence of the interfacial shearing on the nematic director configuration profiles, we investigated its effect in co-current and counter-current flow configurations for both interfacial anchoring conditions up to pressures in the limit of the stability described above to understand how flow influences the stagnant configuration of the LC (see Fig. 1c, d), specifically in proximity of the 5CB-aqueous interface.

Structural transitions in soft-interfaced nematics under bulk flow

The characterization of the pressure-driven flow of nematic 5CB while maintaining a stable 5CB-pure water interface is shown in Fig. 2 for a 20 μm

deep channel. At equal and low inlet pressures of the two co-current phases (e.g. $P_{inlet} = 5$ mbar), the dark optical appearance of the 5CB was consistent with its undeformed state during flow (Fig. 2a). For the measured average velocity (v_{LC}) of 14 $\mu\text{m/s}$ using particle tracking velocimetry, we calculated the Ericksen number with $\eta \sim 100$ mPa s, and $K \sim 10^{-11}$ N, consistent with the elastic contribution of the nematic ordering. Increasing the inlet pressures (to e.g., $P_{inlet} = 10$ mbar, $v_{LC} = 27 \mu\text{m/s}$), we observed an increase in the intensity of the 5CB side under crossed polarizers, indicating a deformation of the nematic director (Fig. 2a). Since we observed a dark appearance when the polarizer and the analyzer were oriented at 0° and 90° (Fig. 2b), respectively; this optical appearance supported a deformation in the direction of the flow as sketched in Fig. 2c, which was known to be the “Bowser” (or Vertical¹⁶) state. Further increasing the inlet pressures resulted in an ordering transition evidenced by a change in the optical appearance of the 5CB side as shown in Fig. 2a for $P_{inlet} = 13$ mbar ($v_{LC} \approx 38 \mu\text{m/s}$) and sketched in Fig. 2c. The resulted director configuration of the nematic phase was previously defined as “Dowser” (or Horizontal¹⁶) state where the local director at the mid-plane of the channel was along the flow direction. For 20 μm deep channels, we observed this transition to occur at $P_{inlet} = 12.2 \pm 2.8$ mbar ($n = 6$), which consistently changed with channel depth (Fig. S3). After transition, we calculated $Er \gg 1$ indicating the dominant viscous effects over the LC elasticity. Further increase in the flow velocities resulted in a change in the optical appearance of the 5CB consistent with the increased average alignment along the direction of flow as suggested by the increased retardation of the transmitted light predicted by the Michel-Levy chart⁶. We note that the uniform appearance of the planar 5CB-water interface was evident in the 5CB side as in its bulk, which was further confirmed by Fluorescence Confocal Polarizing Microscope (FCPM) images collected from the mid-planes and z-stack of the confocal micrographs (Fig. S4). Thus, these optical characteristics are consistent with the shear induced configuration transition sketched in Fig. 2c both for the bulk and the 5CB-water interfaces.

The observations we made on the configuration transitions in bulk LC phase upon pressure-driven flow shown in Fig. 2 are consistent with the configuration transitions observed in their hard-interfaced counterparts (Fig. S5). Such consistency suggested that the LC configurations within the bulk of the LCs are governed by the confining hard (DMOAP-coated glass and PDMS) interfaces of the channels. However, we observed a significant difference in the optical appearance of 5CB side (thus the configurations) at the vicinity of the soft interfaces when the anchoring at that interface was homeotropic. Figure 3 shows the optical appearance of 5CB flowing in a

Fig. 2 | Co-current flow of nematic 5CB and aqueous phases with LC-water interface mediating planar anchoring. The polarized optical micrographs taken from a 20 μm deep microchannel with a 5CB flow with planar 5CB-water interfaces under crossed polarizer and analyzers oriented as (a) 45° and 135° , and (b) 0° and

90° , respectively. c Sketches describing the configurations of 5CB molecules during flow. P_{5CB} and $P_{Aq.}$ designate the inlet pressures of 5CB and the aqueous phases. PDMS designates the polydimethylsiloxane side of the channel. Scale bars: 100 μm .

Fig. 3 | Co-current flow of nematic 5CB and aqueous phases with LC-aqueous interface mediating homeotropic anchoring. The polarized optical micrographs taken from a 20 μm deep microchannel with a 5CB flow with homeotropic 5CB-aqueous interfaces under crossed polarizer and analyzers oriented as (a) 45° and 135°, and (b) 0° and 90°, respectively. 5CB and 1.0 mM sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) phases are flowing co-currently with equal inlet pressures as indicated above the images. (c) Fluorescent confocal polarized micrographs collected from mid-planes

of the channels where the polarization of the excitation light is along the flow direction. (d) Sketches describing the director configurations of 5CB at the mid-planes of the channels during flow. The orange objects indicate the presence of SDS molecules at the 5CB-aqueous interfaces. B and D letters in sketches refer to the Bowser and Dowser states, respectively, maintained at the bulk of the 5CB. Scale bars: (a, b) 100 μm , (a) insets: 20 μm (c) 20 μm . Brightness of the insets in (a) was increased by 30% for increased visibility of the details.

20 μm deep channel where its free interface was in contact with an aqueous solution of 1 mM SDS for homeotropic anchoring. The optical appearance of the bulk of the LC phase as a function of the bulk flow rate (Fig. 3a, b) was similar to the planar soft interfaced (Fig. 2) or the hard interfaced (Fig. S5) flow of 5CB, thus was not influenced by the significant difference in the anchoring condition at the aqueous interface. The homeotropic interfacial alignment of the aqueous interface causes elastic strain at the vicinity of the 5CB-aqueous interface that shows influence on the ordering profile of 5CB for distances $\sim 15 \mu\text{m}$ away from the interface as evidenced by the optical appearance (Fig. 3a, insets). We observed a significant change in the polarized optical appearance of the homeotropic 5CB-aqueous interfaces upon increasing flow rates resulting from the coupling of the orientations of the flow and interfacial anchoring of the mesogens (Fig. 3a, b). This effect was more evident when the flow was increased at the Dowser state (for $P_{\text{inlet}} = 10$ to 50 mbar). Specifically, FCPM images taken with excitation polarization in the direction of the flow show the interfacial region with dark appearance, supporting the orthogonality of the local director to the polarization. The length of this dark interfacial region, also supported by the polarized micrographs, decreased upon increasing the bulk shear of the 5CB (Fig. 3a, c, P_{inlet} of 10 mbar to 50 mbar cases), which evidences a gradual orientation of the local director at the vicinity of the interface parallel to the flow. Such observations indicate the influence of the flow and the interfacial conditions on LC structuring, which resulted in straining of the interfacial nematic director profile as sketched in Fig. 3d. We investigate such effects further below with the application of independent interfacial shear via tuning the flow of 5CB and aqueous phase separately in co-current and counter-current flow configurations.

Shearing of the nematic soft interfaces maintaining planar anchoring

Figure 4a shows the polarized microscopy images of the 5CB-water co-flow system with planar 5CB-water interface under varying applied interfacial shear. In these experiments, 5CB flow was maintained at its Bowser state resulted from the mid-plane flow velocity of $\sim 18 \mu\text{m/s}$ (maintained with $P_{\text{inlet}} = 5$ mbar). The dark appearance of the 5CB-water interface at equal inlet pressures of the two phases became brighter as the flow velocity of the water side was increased (shown as intensity plots and cropped images of the interfaces). This increase in the brightness was due to the elastic deformations in the direction of flow. Although the increase in the brightness was present at the interface under polarized microscopy, we did not observe a significant change in the FCPM images of the channels with interfacial shearing as shown in Fig. 3b. This feature supported that the configuration remained at its Bowser state even at the highest shear conditions although there was a considerable deformation close to the interface. We measured the local velocities at the mid-plane of the channel for the three shear conditions as shown in Fig. 4c. Whereas the velocity profile of the 5CB side appeared uniform for the equal pressure conditions, the influence of the interfacial shear was evident for the unequal pressure cases (Fig. 4a, c, $P_{\text{Aq.}} = 15$ mbar and 25 mbar cases). The interface velocity was measured to be 43 $\mu\text{m/s}$ for $P_{\text{Aq.}} = 15$ mbar, and 58 $\mu\text{m/s}$ for $P_{\text{Aq.}} = 25$ mbar cases. The influence of the interfacial shear on the velocity was evident at distances $\sim 15 \mu\text{m}$ deep into the interface, which was consistent with the length of the shear-induced LC deformations at the interface (intensity plots in Fig. 4a). However, we did not observe a transition to a Dowser state at the vicinity of the interface although we

Fig. 4 | Co-current shearing of LC-water interface mediating planar anchoring. (a) The polarized optical micrographs taken from a 20 μm deep microchannel where weak 5CB flow was maintained with planar 5CB-water interfaces under crossed polarizer and analyzers oriented as 45° and 135° (top), the zoomed images of the interfaces (bottom) (b) FCPM images taken from mid-planes and z-stacks of the images shown in (a). (c) The velocity profiles of the mid-planes of 5CB side upon applied interfacial shear for weak 5CB flow case. (d) The LC configuration sketches of the bulk and the interface before and after interfacial shear for weak 5CB flow. (e) The polarized optical micrographs taken from a 20 μm deep microchannel where

strong 5CB flow was maintained with planar 5CB-water interfaces under crossed polarizer and analyzers oriented as 45° and 135° (top), the zoomed images of the interfaces (bottom) (f) FCPM images taken from mid-planes and z-stacks of the images shown in (e). (g) The velocity profiles of the mid-planes of 5CB side upon applied interfacial shear for strong 5CB flow case. (h) The LC configuration sketches of the bulk and after interfacial shear for strong 5CB flow. The representative guide curves in (c) and (g) are drawn to track the data points. Scale bars: (a, e) 100 μm for polarized micrographs and 20 μm for their zoomed parts, (b) 10 μm , (f) 20 μm .

measured a local velocity ($\sim 58 \mu\text{m/s}$) significantly larger than the velocity ($\sim 38 \mu\text{m/s}$) corresponding to a structural transition observed with bulk flow (Figs. 2 and 3). We hypothesize the absence of such transition to the energetically unfavorable state with the formation of topological defect structures at the interfacial region that would result if the Dowser state formed at the interface. Such observations supported the shear-induced deformations at the vicinity of the interfaces along the direction of flow as depicted in the sketches shown in Fig. 4d.

Figure 4e shows the micrographs collected from an experiment performed when the 5CB flow was maintained at its Dowser state when $P_{5CB} = 30 \text{ mbar}$ but the P_{Aq} was varied. The pale pink hue of Dowser state of 5CB corresponding to $\alpha \approx 60^\circ$ was present when the velocity at the mid-plane was maintained at $\sim 120 \mu\text{m/s}$. At equal P_{inlet} of the two sides, the 5CB-water interface did not show a significant deformation (zoomed images in Fig. 4e). However, when P_{Aq} was increased to 40 and 50 mbar, a green hue at the vicinity of the 5CB-water interface appeared (zoomed images in Fig. 4e). At these conditions, we measured an increased in the local velocity at the 5CB-water interface to reach up to $\sim 200 \mu\text{m/s}$ with interfacial shear (Fig. 4g). Such birefringence color corresponded to $\alpha \approx 68^\circ$, confirming the deformation of the LC ordering at the vicinity of the interface. Such deformations were also supported by the FCPM images shown in Fig. 4f that evidence an increased brightness of the interfaces with increased interfacial shear when the polarization of the excitation light source was along the flow direction. These microscopic observations supported the shear-induced deformations in the Dowser state at the vicinity of the interfaces along the direction of flow as depicted in the sketches shown in Fig. 4h.

Figure 5 shows the optical appearance of the 5CB side during flow when the interfacial shear was applied co-currently or counter-currently in the same channel. As seen in the images in Fig. 5a, the brightness at the vicinity of the interface was monotonously decreased to maintain the dark, Bowser state away from the interface when the interfacial shear was applied co-currently (shown in inset intensity plots). However, with the application of the counter-current shear in the same microfluidic channel with the same P_{5CB} , there existed a dark region $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$ away from the bright 5CB-water interface which was followed by an increased intensity with distance from the interface (shown with yellow arrows in the micrographs and inset intensity plots). We concluded that this dark “band” $\sim 5\text{--}8 \mu\text{m}$ away from the interface is the undeformed nematic director resulting from the counter-current flow of the 5CB and water. Thus, the brighter appearance at the two sides of this dark region indicated the deformation of the LC director towards the two opposite directions along the longitudinal direction of the channel as sketched in Fig. 5b. Consistent with this, we measured the average velocity of the bulk 5CB to be $\sim 19 \mu\text{m/s}$, and the interfacial velocity to be $\sim 15 \mu\text{m/s}$ for counter-current flow of the aqueous phase at the given conditions in Fig. 5a. Such measurements supported the flow profiles of the 5CB side as sketched in Fig. 5b for the two flow cases. We also observed the deformation of the Dowser state to be significantly influenced by the application of the counter-current shear to the interface as shown in Fig. 5c. The counter-current application of the interfacial shear resulted in decreased deformation of the nematic director at the vicinity of the 5CB-water interface. Although the counter-current flow of the water phase was strong, which would have resulted in an elastic deformation in the opposite

Fig. 5 | Influence of the flow configurations on LC director configurations at the vicinity of planar interfaces. (a) Polarized optical micrographs of the weak flow of 5CB and pure water at inlet pressures $P_{5CB} = 10$ mbar and $P_{Aq.} = 20$ mbar in co-current (left) and counter-current (right) flow configuration. (b) Sketches of the LC director profiles for the corresponding conditions shown in (a). (c) Polarized optical micrographs of the strong flow of 5CB and pure water at inlet pressures $P_{5CB} = 40$ mbar and $P_{Aq.} = 60$ mbar in co-current (left) and counter-current (right) flow configuration. Scale bars = 20 μm . The double-sided arrows show the orientations of the polarizer and the analyzer of the microscope. The pink and blue one-sided horizontal arrows show the flow directions of the 5CB and the water phases, respectively.

direction of the 5CB flow, we did not observe such deformation. An indicative of this result was the absence of the dark band at the vicinity of the interface resulting from the transition, which was observed in the weak flow regime in Fig. 5a. The FCPM images also support these observations (Fig. S6). We reasoned such absence to be due to the high energetical cost of maintaining such a configuration at the vicinity of the 5CB-water interface due to the requirement of the two Dowser-to-Bowser transitions bringing significant strain that would result in the formation of two defect lines. Instead, we observed a pink appearance at the interface that corresponds to a lower elastic deformation ($\alpha \approx 46^\circ$) than the bulk ($\alpha \approx 52^\circ$), both in the direction of the 5CB flow.

Shearing of the nematic soft interfaces maintaining homeotropic anchoring

Shearing of the interfaces mediating homeotropic anchoring raises questions regarding the structures of the interfaces under applied shear as the average bulk director, the interfacial director, and the applied shear are all

orthogonal to each other in stagnant conditions (Fig. 1d). The co-current flow of the aqueous solution of 1 mM SDS and 5CB within the microchannels is shown in Fig. 6. At such flow configuration, the bright appearance of the 5CB-aqueous interface of the Bowser state of the LCs ($P_{inlet} = 5$ mbar) was evident in polarized optical micrographs shown in Fig. 6a, b. The bright appearance of the interface was observed to be thickened when the interfacial shear was increased. At equal 5CB and aqueous phase inlet pressures ($P_{5CB} = P_{Aq.} = 5$ mbar), the appearance of the birefringent fringes at the 5CB-aqueous interfaces was supportive of the configuration shown in Fig. 6d at low interfacial shear. Upon increasing the interfacial shear, we observed a transition to a texture with an appearance of a dark line parallel to the 5CB-aqueous interface as shown by a blue arrow in Fig. 6a, b. Such a line was an indicative of a line defect formation as suggested by the previous literature on the nematic configurations at the vicinity of the homeotropic, hard interfaces^{19,42}. The mid-plane and z-stacked cross-section FCPM micrographs taken at the given conditions of the same channel shown in Fig. 6c also revealed thickening of the interfacial region and an increase in the intensity of the emitted light at the vicinity of the 5CB-aqueous interface with increased interfacial shear reaching to intensities significantly higher than the bulk (more FCPM images available in Fig. S7a). This optical appearance further supported the orientation of the LC interfacial director along with the shear direction. With such evidence, we concluded that the shear-induced configurations of the Bowser state at the vicinity of the homeotropic soft interfaces to be the profiles sketched in Fig. 6d.

The co-current shear-dependent optical appearance of the homeotropic 5CB-aqueous interface when the bulk Dowser state was maintained is shown in Fig. 6e, f. We observed that the dark band at the vicinity of the interface (shown with blue arrow in Fig. 6e) for the equal inlet pressures case of the two phases diminished when the interfacial shear was increased (insets in Fig. 6e for detail). Such a change in the optical appearance suggests a configuration transition upon applied interfacial shear. Consistently, the FCPM images also indicated a change in the appearance of the aqueous interface of the 5CB side upon increasing shear (Fig. 6g and the intensity plots) with an increased intensity at the interface and disappearance of the dark band close to the interface when the excitation light polarization was at 30° and 45° (further images in Fig. S7b). These observations indicated an average orientation of the director at the vicinity of the interface to maintain an ordering closer to the direction of the flow and to result in a configuration profile as sketched in Fig. 6h.

When the homeotropic 5CB-aqueous interface was sheared counter-currently at the weak 5CB flow, shearing did not cause a significant change in the optical appearance of the aqueous interface, indicating the absence of a significant structural transition as shown in Fig. 7a, b. However, FCPM images in Fig. 7c show a decrease in the intensity of the interfacial region when the excitation polarization was 45° , whereas an increase was observed when the polarization was 135° . Such evidence indicated that the average orientation of the local nematic director at the vicinity of the aqueous interface was tilted towards the counter-current flow direction of the aqueous phase. However, the absence of a significant change in the intensity of the interfacial region when the excitation polarization was along the flow direction showed that the local director was not completely aligned towards the flow direction (further images in Fig. S8a). Thus, we arrived at the conclusion of the configuration sketch shown in Fig. 7d, which indicates the shear-induced ordering of the mesogens at the vicinity of the interface towards the flow direction.

For counter-current shear applied to the homeotropic LC interface at strong flow, we observed that the optical appearance of the 5CB side at the vicinity of the interface was changed as shown in Fig. 7e, f (insets for closer images). For the imaging configuration shown in Fig. 7e, we observed a decrease in the brightness of the 5CB side close to the interface as the interfacial shear was increased. We related this change in the optical appearance to the change in the orientation of the interfacial mesogens towards the flow direction of the aqueous phase. Investigation of the FCPM images at the three conditions presented in Fig. 7g (further images in

Fig. 6 | Co-current interfacial shearing of LC-water interface mediating homeotropic anchoring. The polarized optical micrographs taken from a 20 μm deep microchannel with a weak 5CB flow with homeotropic aqueous interface under crossed polarizer and analyzers oriented as (a) 45° and 135°, and (b) 0° and 90°, respectively. 5CB and aqueous solution of 1 mM SDS are flowing co-currently with the inlet pressures as indicated above the images. (c) Fluorescent confocal polarized micrographs collected from mid-planes (top) and the z-stacks (bottom) of the channels in (a) where the polarization of the excitation light is along the flow direction. The intensity plot shows the profiles associated with the arrows indicated in (c). (d) Sketches describing the LC director profiles at low and high interfacial

shearing of weak 5CB flow. The polarized optical micrographs taken from the same microchannel with a strong 5CB flow under crossed polarizer and analyzers oriented as (e) 45° and 135°, and (f) 0° and 90°, respectively. (g) Fluorescent confocal polarized micrographs collected from mid-planes of the channels in (e) at the polarization of the excitation light as shown in the images (30° for top, 45° for bottom image). The intensity plots show the profiles associated with the arrows indicated in (g). (h) Sketches describing the LC director profiles at low and high interfacial shearing of strong 5CB flow. Scale bars: Scale bars: (a, b, e, f) 100 μm , insets: 20 μm , (c, g) 20 μm , z-stack 10 μm .

Fig. S7b) showed that the alignment of the interfacial director was not completely parallel to the interface. Instead, they were tilted $\sim 45^\circ$ normal to the interface as revealed by the increase in the intensity of the interfacial region with shear when the polarization of the excitation light source was 135° (bottom row). At this configuration of imaging, we observed a region with dark optical appearance next to the bright interfacial region. This dark region was observed to move deeper into the 5CB side due to the configuration transition at the interface upon increased interfacial shear. When the imaging was performed at 60° of the excitation polarization, we observed the brighter appearance of the same region that appeared dark when 135° of the excitation polarization. In addition, we observed that the initially monotonous change in the brightness of the interface at this imaging condition when the imaging was performed at $P_{5CB} = P_{Aq} = 20$ mbar was changed to an image with a non-monotonous distribution of the intensity profile as a function of the distance from the interface. Such evidence also supports the alignment of the interfacial mesogens with flow and the shear-induced configuration transition in the 5CB side upon the applied interfacial shear. With such analysis, we defined the low- and high- interfacial shear configurations of the Dowser state of the 5CB to be the sketches shown in Fig. 7h.

Discussion

The flow of nematic LC and aqueous phases in microchannels while maintaining a stable soft interface allowed us to identify the bulk and interfacial shear-induced structural changes in the flowing nematic phases.

We observed that the interfacial shearing resulted in significant changes in the nematic director profiles in proximity of the soft interfaces. Such influence ranged from simple straining of the director to the formation of defect structures upon increasing shear depending on the orthogonality of the local nematic directors in bulk and at the interfaces, and the flow directions of the two distinct phases. The strained interfacial LC region extended up to $\sim 15 \mu\text{m}$ distances away from the aqueous interfaces, indicating a significant storage of elastic energy close to the aqueous interfaces that simulate the successful confined systems present in the literature^{2,3,43,44}. Such influence was shown to occur both in the planar and homeotropic LC interfaces, and both in the co-current and counter-current flow configurations of the LC and aqueous phases, which was not possible without the application of bulk flow and interfacial shearing at the same time. The thickness of the region where the influence of interfacial shear is observed was consistent with the aspect ratio of the microchannels. The 20 μm deep and 250 μm wide side hosting a stable 5CB flow in contact with an aqueous phase, had an aspect ratio of 12.5. The attained aspect ratio was the reason for the reduced influence of hard interfaces on the overall bulk director field.

We estimate the shear stress induced by the aqueous phase to range from the order of 0.1 Pa (5 mbar inlet pressure) to 1 Pa (25 mbar inlet pressure) that result in significant structural transitions observed as in Figs. 4a, 6a and 7a, where planar (Fig. 4a) and homeotropic (Figs. 6a, 7a) anchoring was maintained at their interfaces, respectively. We observed such shearing to result in significant elastic deformations in planar aqueous interfaces in co-current flow configurations (Fig. 4a) and in homeotropic

Fig. 7 | Counter-current interfacial shearing of LC-water interface mediating homeotropic anchoring. The polarized optical micrographs taken from a 20 μm deep microchannel with a weak 5CB flow with homeotropic 5CB-aqueous interfaces under crossed polarizer and analyzers oriented as (a) 45° and 135°, and (b) 0° and 90°, respectively. 5CB and aqueous phase are flowing co-currently with the inlet pressures as indicated above the images. (c) Fluorescent confocal polarized micrographs collected from mid-planes of the channels in (a) where the polarization of the excitation light is shown in the images. The intensity plot shows the profiles associated to the arrows indicated in (c). (d) Sketches describing the LC director

configurations at low and high interfacial shearing of weak 5CB flow. The polarized optical micrographs taken from the same microchannel with a strong 5CB flow under crossed polarizer and analyzers oriented as (e) 45° and 135°, and (f) 0° and 90°, respectively. (g) Fluorescent confocal polarized micrographs collected from mid-planes of the channels in (d) where the polarization of the excitation light is shown in the images. (h) Sketches describing the LC director configurations at low and high interfacial shearing of strong 5CB flow. Scale bars: (a, b, e, f) 100 μm , insets: 50 μm , (c, g) 10 μm . Brightness of the insets in (a) was increased by 30% for increased visibility of the details.

interfaces in counter-current flow configurations (Fig. 7a) whereas the same magnitude of shearing induced an ordering transition that led to the formation of defect structures nearby the homeotropic interfaces in co-current flow configurations (Fig. 6a). We observed that the interfacial shearing does not immediately cause the same structural transitions at the interfaces that can directly be correlated to the independent effect of the shear caused by the bulk flow. Instead, it appeared that the elastic energy contribution at the interfacial region plays a critical role in the resulting nematic director configurations upon interfacial shearing that is a function of the shear profiles and anchoring conditions close to the LC-aqueous interfaces.

Based on the structural characterizations we performed using mid-plane FCPM images above, we sketched the proposed 3D nematic director configurations as summarized in Fig. 8. These observations we present here are significant in the context that such a small amount of shear induces considerable structural transitions at the vicinity of the interfaces causing a significant energetical penalty arising from the elastic deformations and the formation of defects. Past studies suggest that such effects, i.e. simple deformations and structural transitions at the vicinity of the interfaces, or presence of the defects, are useful tools to design functional, responsive LC

interfaces^{3,45–48}. In most of the cases, such structures play a critical role in the functionality of the designed systems. In the platform we develop herein, we show that these structures can be generated on demand by independently controlling the interfacial and bulk shear. Such a capability adds additional modality to the next generation LC-based responsive platforms.

To strengthen the validity of the configurations presented in Fig. 8, we conducted Boltzmann numerical simulations⁴⁹ based on the nemato-hydrodynamic equations that describe the dynamics of the LC director field coupled to the flow field^{50–52} (for detailed methodology see the “Numerical Model” section). Figure 9a illustrates a schematic of the computational domain, which is defined as a 3D channel surrounded by rigid walls at the top and bottom, as well as on the left and right sides, with periodic boundary conditions applied in the flow direction. Utilizing a dynamic phase-field approach, we separate the LC from the isotropic fluid to simulate a soft interface, thereby replicating the experimental setup. Additionally, normal anchoring conditions are enforced at both the top and bottom walls, as well as at the soft interface. An independent pressure gradient is then applied throughout the channel to the LC and the isotropic fluid to realize independent flow states. Specifically, we

Fig. 8 | The summary of the proposed nematic LC director configurations. The sketches show the director profiles for (a) planar and (b) homeotropic LC-aqueous interfaces. Bowser and Dowser indicate the structures maintained in bulk of the LC

phase. The red circular symbols in the aqueous and LC side of the channels indicate the flow directions of the phases.

Fig. 9 | Simulation results of the microfluidic LC flow with aqueous interfaces. (a) This snapshot displays the geometry of the simulation domain, which consists of a 3D channel with periodic boundary conditions in the flow direction. The LC phase is on the left side, while the aqueous phase is on the right side, forming a soft interface at the center. Co-current flow is achieved by independently imposing a pressure gradient in the two branches. Yellow rods indicate the anchoring conditions of the LC at both the soft interface and the solid walls. Colored arrows at the mid-channel, along with the background color plot, illustrate the resulting velocity distribution. ∇p_{LC}

and ∇p_{iso} indicates the pressure gradients for flow of the LC and isotropic (aqueous) phases. The steady configurations of the nematic LCs are shown at (b) Bowser, low interfacial shear, (c) Bowser, high interfacial shear, (d) Dowser, low interfacial shear, and (e) Dowser, high interfacial shear, along with the corresponding cross-polarizer textures. The disclination line in panel (c) has been colored in purple. The intensity distribution of transmitted polarized light for the various LC configurations and interfacial shear conditions is presented (f) from simulations and (g) from experiments, drawn using the micrographs shown in Fig. 6.

analyze the scenario of co-current flow with homeotropic anchoring while varying the pressure gradient for both the LC and liquid phases. The resulting structures are displayed in Fig. 9b–e, accompanied by their corresponding textures observed under cross-polarization. The numerical findings align well with the experimental results shown in Fig. 6, which feature co-current flow and homeotropic interfacial anchoring

conditions, as well as with the snapshots of LC configurations summarized in Fig. 8b. Furthermore, to validate the correspondence between our simulations (Fig. 9b–e) and the structures observed experimentally, we present in Fig. 9f, g the transmission intensity distributions of polarized light measured in both simulations and experiments, respectively, which demonstrate good qualitative agreement.

Initial numerical results (not presented here) indicate that the competition between anchoring at the solid walls (top and bottom) and the soft interface may play a crucial role in selecting specific topological states. We will explore this further in our future research.

The findings we report on the shear-induced structuring of the LC phases are promising in the context of several future applications and the fundamental knowledge on the topological transitions in anisotropic media. First, the presence of such effect is significant as the straining of the LCs has been shown to be critically in the sensitivity of the LC interfaces in response to the changes induced externally by the adsorption of molecules, induction of electrical or magnetic fields among others^{3,10,43,53,54}. Thus, straining the LC director profiles via shear on demand will be significantly advantageous in tuning the sensitivity of the sensor platforms built based on the concept we introduce here. Second, the LC interfaces were shown to be a useful anisotropic medium for the controlled synthesis of anisotropic, nanostructured nanomaterials^{4,11,55,56}. The two-phase microfluidic platform we realized here represents a promising improvement in the control over the structures of the synthesized materials as well as developing controlled processes for their continuous synthesis. Third, we presented the structural transitions in the nematic LC phases upon applied bulk and interfacial shear. However, such knowledge can be extended to more complex LC phases such as cholesterics (2D ordering), blue phases (3D ordering) as well as ferroelectric nematic phases (polar ordering), which would bring more complexity to the LC configurations and will provide promise to the applications that can be developed based on the LC two-phase platform.

In the context of the characterizations on the influence of the bulk and interfacial shearing on LC director configurations and flow profiles we presented in this manuscript, the future efforts will be to employ such interfaces to design automated flow devices for advanced, high-throughput analytical methods, to utilize the interfaces for self-organization of the nanoscopic or microscopic species, and to provide a platform for the synthesis of nanostructured functional materials.

Methods

Materials

The nematic liquid crystal 4-cyano-4'-pentylbiphenyl (5CB) was purchased from HCCCH Jiangsu Hecheng Chemical Materials Co., Ltd. (Nanjing, China). Glass slides were purchased from Marienfeld GmbH (Lauda-Königshofen, Germany). HPLC-grade acetone, 2-propanol, and hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS), trichloro(octadecyl)silane (OTS), dimethyloctadecyl[3-(trimethoxysilyl)propyl]ammonium chloride (DMOAP), sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), and Nile Red dye were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Deionized water used in the experiments was produced with a resistance of 18.2 M Ω .cm with a Heal Force water purification system. Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) Sylgard™ 184 Silicone Elastomer Kit was purchased from Dow Europe GmbH (Wiesbaden, Germany). The photoresist AZ P4620, AZ EBR solvent, AZ 400 K developer 1:4, Buffered Oxide Etchant 7:1 (BOE) were supplied from Microchemicals GmbH (Ulm, Germany). The Polos spin coater, hot plate and Nanowriter were purchased from SPS-Europe B.V. (Putten, The Netherlands). Oxygen plasma device was purchased from Diener Electronics (Ebhausen, Germany). OB1 MK3+ flow controller was supplied from ElveFlow (Paris, France). Sulfate modified fluorescent polystyrene particles with 1.0 μ m bead diameter were supplied from Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc. (Waltham, MA, USA).

Fabrication of microchannels

The overall fabrication of procedure of the microfluidic channel is shown in Fig. 10 and the channel design is shown in Fig. S1. The glass slides were first sonicated for 15 min in acetone, and then in 2-propanol for initial cleaning purposes. After the solvent treatment, HMDS vapor deposition was applied on glass slides for 5 min under vacuum at 150°C to maintain hydrophobicity and enhance the attachment of the photoresist during wet etching. The

a Chemical vapor deposition of HMDS

b Photoresist coating and photolithography

c Development of the photoresist

d Isotropic wet etching of the microchannel

e Photoresist stripping

f PDMS bonding after O₂ plasma treatment

Fig. 10 | Fundamental steps representing the microfluidic channel fabrication. (a) HMDS coating on glass slide by chemical vapor deposition. (b) Maskless photolithography. (c) The development of the positive photoresist. (d) The channel cavity after isotropic wet etching (e) Shape of the patterned glass after the photoresist stripping. (f) The microchannel is ready after glass-PDMS bonding with O₂ plasma treatment.

positive photoresist AZ P4620 was diluted with EBR solvent, in a ratio of 1:1 or 2:1 and coated on HMDS-treated glass slides with POLOS spin coater. The preferred dilution ratio was set depending on the final desired channel depth. A homogeneous photoresist coating was ensured with the spin coater reaching a spin speed of 1000 rpm for 50 sec, between the linearly

accelerating and decelerating parts for 10 sec each. The photoresist-coated substrates were first soft baked at 110 °C for 50 sec and were cooled down to the room temperature and equilibrated for 10 min, then photolithography was performed with an exposure dose of 160 mJ/cm² in the Nanowriter, which was equipped with a 405 nm laser. The developing step was performed using the AZ 400 K developer solution for 80 sec, and 2 min for 14 μm and 20 μm deep channels, respectively. The photoresist of the patterned glass slide was hard baked for 90 min on a hot plate at 110 °C before etching.

The patterned glass slides were naturally cooled down to room temperature and equilibrated for at least 2 hours. The isotropic wet etching was done by placing the glass slides vertically in a PTFE beaker filled with 7:1 BOE solution and the glass slides were etched in an ultrasonic bath for 20 min. The etching duration was adjusted to be 20 min or 30 min for 14 μm and 20 μm deep channels, respectively, since the constant etching rate of 700 nm/min was attained. The upper temperature limit for etching was set to approximately 28 °C for smooth, consistent etching of channel edges. After etching, the glass slides were rinsed in deionized water with two steps, and they were subsequently placed in acetone for photoresist stripping. The stripping was performed in an ultrasonic bath for 10 min. After stripping the photoresist, the glass slides were rinsed with ample amounts of acetone, pure water, and 2-propanol without allowing them to dry to remove any residues from the surface. The glass-slides were finally dried to prepare for glass-PDMS bonding (Fig. S1a). The depths of the channels were measured to be 20 ± 0.4 μm (n = 15).

Preparation and functionalization of the microfluidic device

PDMS was prepared by mixing the elastomer base and curing agent with a 10:1 mass ratio for 5 min to ensure homogeneous mixing. The mixture was left under vacuum for 30 min in order to remove bubbles. The cover pieces for flat PDMS elastomers were prepared on OTS-coated glass slides. The OTS deposition of glass slides was done in advance in a vacuum chamber for at least 30 min. The transparent mixture of PDMS was poured onto the prepared slides and cured at 60 °C for 2 hours in an oven. After that the PDMS pieces were cooled down to the room temperature, the etched glass slide was bonded to a flat PDMS elastomer of desired area, which was priorly punched with a 1.5 mm biopsy punch for inlet and outlet ports of the channels. The glass-PDMS bonding was performed by oxygen plasma treatment. The PDMS surface and etched glass were exposed to oxygen gas stream for 30 sec under vacuum (chamber was priorly vacuumed for 2 min) and then plasma was applied for 20 sec. After this step, the channel-etched glass slide and PDMS elastomer were bonded to complete the microfluidic channel fabrication. The plasma treatment modifies the properties of surface, namely makes glass and PDMS surfaces hydrophilic. To feed the inlet materials to the channel, 1.5 mm PTFE tubings were connected when necessary and tubings were also connected to the microfluidic flow controller system (Fig. S1b). To allow 5CB and aqueous flow in contact, the surface chemistry was changed with DMOAP functionalization to maintain a hydrophobic surface (Fig. S1d,e). The pressure-driven flow along the experiments was ensured by using Elveflow OB1 MK3+ Flow Controller. DMOAP solution of 1 volume % was prepared and introduced to the channel from the tubing at one-side of the channel. It is worth highlighting that ensuring homogeneous DMOAP functionalization is critical for ultimately achieving a stable virtual walled flow system. The optimum inlet pressure of DMOAP solution and pure water was set to 150 mbar to achieve a stable flow of 5CB and water after the functionalization of surfaces. The neighboring flow of DMOAP solution and water were kept constant for 30 min. After this DMOAP functionalization period, the tubing feeding DMOAP was gently removed from the channel and the whole channel cavity was rinsed with water for at least 15 min. 5CB flow was started while water was continued to be fed from the other inlet (water flow was not ceased to eliminate the risk of contamination or loss of hydrophobicity). As 5CB flowed along one path of the channel a virtual wall was formed between 5CB and water, as also previously described to be stable elsewhere³⁷.

Microscopy

The flow was imaged using a Zeiss LSM 900 Fluorescence Confocal Polarizing Microscope (Jena, Germany). Crossed linear polarizer and analyzers were used in polarized optical microscopy images, either being 45° and 135° or 0° and 90° rotated. The flow of 5CB and aqueous phases during the experiments were all horizontal from the top-view (x-y plane), namely along 0° direction of polarizer and analyzer. Michel-Lévy Interference Color Chart was used to analyze the POM images and provide comments on the molecular alignment of 5CB molecules based on their optical appearance. For this purpose, we used the characterizations described elsewhere^{6,57} to determine the magnitude of deformation for the nematic director. Since the ordinary and extraordinary refractive indices of nematic 5CB is known (1.5296 and 1.711, respectively), we estimated the director distortion with angle α by using the channel depth (20 μm) and reported when needed. In 20 μm deep channels, when the angle α was at its maximum, the interference colors reached a maximum of third order.

In confocal imaging, Nile Red was dissolved in 5CB with 0.01 wt % as a fluorophore to perceive the orientation 5CB mesogens since Nile Red ($\lambda_{ex} = 549$ nm, $\lambda_{em} = 628$ nm)⁵⁸. The excitation laser source has 561 nm wavelength, and the pinhole was set to 78 μm. Confocal images were taken with 5% intensity and 750 V master gain from 40x objective. Such configuration corresponding to the 3.06 μm thickness of the imaging plane. In some of the experiments, particle tracking velocimetry was used to detect the 5CB velocity using sulfate modified fluorescent polystyrene particles. The particles from the half-depth of the channels were observed with fluorescence microscopy with respect to their distances to the LC-water interface.

Performing the flow experiments

All the flow experiments were conducted at room conditions. During the experiments, the inlet pressures of 5CB and aqueous phases were adjusted using the flow controllers. Each single pressure outlet was connected to a tubing which feeds either 5CB or aqueous phase to channel inlets with the pressure values set from the software. In the experiments where bulk flow effects were studied, the inlet pressures of the two phases were equal to each other, and they were modified by the same increments at the same time. To change the inlet pressure values in interfacial shearing experiments, step inputs were given to the pressure of the desired phase, aqueous phase in our study, whereas the pressure of 5CB was set to be constant. After investigating the effect of interfacial shearing at a constant 5CB inlet pressure, the pressure of 5CB was increased to a higher value at which it was again kept constant; while the pressure of the aqueous phase was adjusted. The inlet pressures of 5CB were always set to be the lowest to start the experiment, and then increased to higher values in each set. In the experiments in which homeotropic anchoring of 5CB at aqueous interface was needed, 1 mM sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) solution was prepared in pure water. The experimental path for increasing the inlet pressures of each phase was the same as the experiments in which 5CB had planar anchoring at the aqueous interface.

We repeated each experiment reported in this article multiple times and reported the representative microscopic appearances in the figures. The information on the number of each experiment is available in Table S1 of the Supplementary Information.

Numerical Model

To simulate the LC-water interface in Fig. 9 we consider a 3D computational box with rigid walls in the y and z direction, and periodic boundary condition in the flow direction, i.e. x direction. We introduce the incompressible velocity field $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ and the nematic Q -tensor $\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{r}, t)$, whose principal eigenvector \mathbf{n} , the so-called *director field*, defines the local direction of alignment of the LC. Furthermore, we consider the scalar field $\phi(\mathbf{r}, t)$, measuring the relative concentration of LC with respect to isotropic fluid^{50–52}.

The equilibrium of the LC is defined by the following Landau-De Gennes' free energy

$$\mathcal{F} = \int d\mathbf{r} (f^\phi + f^{\text{bulk}} + f^{\text{el}} + f^{\text{anch}}), \quad (1)$$

where f^ϕ and f^{bulk} are the bulk free energy densities for the ϕ -field and Q -tensor, respectively, f^{el} defines the energy cost of elastic deformations of the LC, and f^{anch} its anchoring properties to the domain boundary. In particular,

$$f^\phi = \frac{a}{4}\phi^2(\phi - \phi_0)^2 + \frac{k}{2}(\nabla\phi)^2. \quad (2)$$

For $a, k > 0$, f^ϕ describes a phase separating field with equilibrium values at 0 and ϕ_0 , forming soft interfaces with thickness $\lambda = \sqrt{2k/a}$ and surface tension $\sigma = \sqrt{8ak/9}$. The bulk contribution to the LC free energy

$$f^{\text{bulk}} = A_0 \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\chi(\phi)}{3} \right) \text{Tr} \mathbf{Q}^2 - \frac{\chi(\phi)}{3} \text{Tr} \mathbf{Q}^3 + \frac{\chi(\phi)}{4} (\text{Tr} \mathbf{Q}^2)^2 \right], \quad (3)$$

where, the bulk constant $A_0 > 0$ and $\chi(\phi)$ is a temperature-like parameter that controls the isotropic-nematic transition occurring for $\chi(\phi) > \chi_{cr} = 2.7$. We choose $\chi(\phi) = \chi_0 + \chi_s \phi$, with $\chi_0 < \chi_{cr}$ and $\chi_s > 0$ (see below for the values used in simulations) to confine the LC within the region where $\phi > \phi_0/2$.

The elastic free energy density

$$f^{\text{el}} = \frac{L}{2}(\nabla\mathbf{Q})^2, \quad (4)$$

with L the elastic constant in the single elastic constant approximation. Finally, the anchoring free energy can be further decomposed in two contributions

$$f^{\text{anch}} = f^{\text{anch,soft}} + f^{\text{anch,wall}}, \quad (5)$$

where

$$f^{\text{anch,soft}} = W^{\text{soft}} \nabla\phi \cdot \mathbf{Q} \cdot \nabla\phi, \quad (6)$$

defines the anchoring properties of the LC to the soft (liquid) interface. The anchoring to the solid walls is specified by

$$f^{\text{anch,wall}} = W^{\text{wall}} \sum_i w(d_i) \mathbf{n}_i \cdot \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{r}) \cdot \mathbf{n}_i, \quad (7)$$

where the summation runs over the different boundaries of the box, \mathbf{n}_i and d_i are the normal to the i -th boundary and the distance of the point \mathbf{r} from the i -th boundary, respectively, with $w(x) = \frac{2}{\cosh^2(x)}$. For $W^{\text{soft}} > 0$ (< 0) tangential (homeotropic) anchoring is imposed.

The dynamics is governed by the following evolution equations:

$$D_t \phi = M \nabla^2 \mu, \quad (8)$$

$$D_t \mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{Q}) + \frac{1}{\Gamma} \mathbf{H}, \quad (9)$$

$$\rho D_t \mathbf{v} = -\nabla p + \eta \nabla^2 \mathbf{v} + \nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\sigma}^\phi + \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{\text{LC}}) + \mathbf{F}, \quad (10)$$

where $D_t = \partial_t + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla$ is the material derivative. Equation (9) is an advection-diffusion equation for the concentration field ϕ , with M the mobility parameter and $\mu = \frac{\delta \mathcal{F}}{\delta \phi}$ the chemical potential.

Equation (10) is the Beris-Edwards equation for Q -tensor dynamics. The operator

$$\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{Q}) = (\xi \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{Q}) \left(\mathbf{Q} + \frac{\mathbf{I}}{3} \right) + (\xi \mathbf{D} - \mathbf{Q}) \left(\mathbf{Q} + \frac{\mathbf{I}}{3} \right) - 2\xi \left(\mathbf{Q} + \frac{\mathbf{I}}{3} \right) \text{Tr}(\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{W}), \quad (11)$$

is the co-rotational derivative and defines the response of the Q -tensor to straining and rotational flows, being $\mathbf{D} = (\mathbf{W} + \mathbf{W}^T)/2$ the strain-rate tensor and $\boldsymbol{\Omega} = (\mathbf{W} - \mathbf{W}^T)/2$ the vorticity tensor, namely the symmetric and anti-symmetric part of the gradient velocity $\mathbf{W} = \nabla \mathbf{v}$. The flow-alignment parameter ξ determines the response of the LC to a shear-flow. Here we choose $\xi = 0.7$ to consider flow-aligning rod-like molecules. The molecular field

$$\mathbf{H} = -\frac{\delta \mathcal{F}}{\delta \mathbf{Q}} + \frac{\mathbf{I}}{3} \text{Tr} \left(\frac{\delta \mathcal{F}}{\delta \mathbf{Q}} \right), \quad (12)$$

drives the LC towards equilibrium, at a rate given by the rotational viscosity Γ .

Finally, Eq. (11) is the Navier-Stokes equation ruling the evolution of the flow field. Here, ρ is the constant uniform density, p the hydrodynamic pressure ensuring fluid incompressibility, η the fluid viscosity. The stress tensor has been divided in two contributions:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^\phi = \left(f^\phi - \phi \frac{\delta \mathcal{F}}{\delta \phi} \right) \mathbf{I} - \frac{\delta \mathcal{F}}{\delta (\nabla \phi)} \nabla \phi, \quad (13)$$

accounting for the stress arising from internal structure of the soft interface, and

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{\text{LC}} = -\xi \mathbf{H} \left(\mathbf{Q} + \frac{\mathbf{I}}{3} \right) - \xi \left(\mathbf{Q} + \frac{\mathbf{I}}{3} \right) \mathbf{H} + 2\xi \left(\mathbf{Q} - \frac{\mathbf{I}}{3} \right) \text{Tr} \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{H} + \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{H} - \mathbf{H} \mathbf{Q} - \nabla \mathbf{Q} \cdot \frac{\delta \mathcal{F}}{\delta (\nabla \mathbf{Q})}, \quad (14)$$

is the stress generated by LC deformations. The last term on the right-hand side of Eq. (11) is a force density which enforces the pressure gradient in the channel direction:

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{F}^{\text{LC}} = -\frac{\Delta p^{\text{LC}}}{L_x} \hat{\mathbf{i}} & \text{if } \phi > \frac{\phi_0}{2}, \\ \mathbf{F}^{\text{iso}} = -\frac{\Delta p^{\text{iso}}}{L_x} \hat{\mathbf{i}} & \text{if } \phi < \frac{\phi_0}{2}, \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where Δp^{LC} , Δp^{iso} are the pressure difference at the inlet and outlet of the channel, of length L_x , in the region occupied by the LC and by the isotropic fluid, respectively. To consider co-current flows we set $(\Delta p^{\text{LC}})(\Delta p^{\text{iso}}) > 0$.

Boundary and initial conditions. We impose periodic boundary conditions in the channel direction and no-slip boundary conditions for the velocity field ($\mathbf{v} = 0$) at the solid walls, located at $y = 0, L_y$ and $z = 0, L_z$.

For the concentration field we require

$$\begin{cases} \phi(y = 0) = \phi_0, \\ \phi(y = L_y) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

and impose non-wetting boundary conditions by enforcing

$$\begin{cases} \nabla_\perp \mu = 0, \\ \nabla_\perp (\nabla^2 \phi) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

where ∇_\perp denotes the partial derivative in the normal direction to the walls and directed towards the bulk. We set free boundary conditions for the Q -tensor, since its orientational properties at the boundary are defined by the equilibrium anchoring introduced in the free energy contribution in Eqs. (5–7).

We initialize the concentration field as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \phi(y < L_y/2) = \phi_0, \\ \phi(y > L_y/2) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

and let the ϕ -field relax with $\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{0}$. Once the ϕ -field has reached equilibrium we use this equilibrated configuration as the initial condition for the numerical experiment. We then initialize the Q -tensor randomly and $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{0}$.

Simulation protocol and parameters. We integrate the nemato-hydrodynamic Eqs. (9)–(11) with a predictor-corrector hybrid lattice Boltzmann algorithm [...] consisting of solving Eqs. (9, 10) with a finite-difference algorithm implementing first-order up-wind scheme and fourth-order accurate stencils for space derivatives, and the Navier-Stokes equation through a predictor-corrector LB scheme on a D3Q15 lattice. For technical details on the lattice Boltzmann method here implemented refer to ref. 49.

The numerical parameters are provided in the following in lattice units:

$$\begin{aligned} a &= 0.1, k = 0.04, \phi_0 = 2, A_0 = 0.1, \chi_0 = 2.45, \\ \chi_s &= 0.55, L = 0.01, W^{\text{soft}} = -0.01, \\ W^{\text{wall}}(y = 0) &= 0.01, W^{\text{wall}}(z = 0, L_z) = -0.08, \\ M &= 1, \xi = 0.7, \Gamma = 10, \rho = 2, \eta = 3.3. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, we consider:

- $F^{\text{LC}} = 3 \times 10^{-6}$, $F^{\text{iso}} = 3 \times 10^{-6}$ for the low-shear Bowser state in Fig. 9b;
- $F^{\text{LC}} = 3 \times 10^{-6}$, $F^{\text{iso}} = 1.5 \times 10^{-5}$ for the high-shear Bowser state in Fig. 9c;
- $F^{\text{LC}} = 2 \times 10^{-5}$, $F^{\text{iso}} = 2 \times 10^{-5}$ for the low-shear Dowser state in Fig. 9d;
- $F^{\text{LC}} = 2 \times 10^{-5}$, $F^{\text{iso}} = 3.3 \times 10^{-5}$ for the high-shear Dowser state in Fig. 9e.

For all simulations the computational box has dimensions $L_x = 256$, $L_y = 256$, $L_z = 96$. The numerical code is parallelized with MPI.

Cross-polarizer textures. Cross-polarizer textures can be obtained by recovering the dielectric anisotropy tensor ϵ_{ij} from the Q -tensor⁵¹

$$Q_{ij} = \epsilon_{ij} - \frac{\text{Tr}\epsilon}{3}. \quad (19)$$

The tensor ϵ_{ij} is an operator that, when applied to the unit vector $|\mathbf{e}_{in}\rangle$ representing the polarization of incident light, return the outgoing polarization state vector $|\mathbf{e}_{out}\rangle = \epsilon|\mathbf{e}_{in}\rangle$. To obtain the cross-polarizer textures from the Q -tensor configurations in Fig. 9(b–c) we place the system between a light polarizer at position $z = 0$ and an analyzer at position $z = L_z$, so that the normalized intensity of the extracted light is given by

$$I(\mathbf{r}_\perp) = |\langle \mathbf{e}_A | \hat{\mathbf{P}} | \mathbf{e}_P \rangle|^2, \quad (20)$$

where \mathbf{r}_\perp represents the position in the xy plane normal to the direction z of propagation of light, and \mathbf{e}_P (\mathbf{e}_A) denotes the orientation of the polarizer (analyzer). The projection operator $\hat{\mathbf{P}}$ is computed recursively from the dielectric anisotropy matrix:

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}} = \mathbf{e}_{L_z} \mathbf{e}_{L_z-1} \dots \mathbf{e}_1, \quad (21)$$

with the subscript labelling consecutive planes perpendicular to the z -direction.

Statistical analysis

The sample sizes (n) and error bars are defined in the text when needed. The data were reported as mean \pm standard deviation.

Data availability

All raw experimental data supporting the findings of this study are openly available on <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14960015>. Numerical data and scripts are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14961875>.

Code availability

Necessary information to reproduce the simulated data is provided in the “Methods”. Original scripts and configurations presented in Fig. 9 are openly available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14961875>.

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Author contributions

G.I. conducted experiments and characterizations. L.N.C. performed numerical simulations. E.B. supervised the research. All authors contributed to data interpretation, discussions, and manuscript preparation.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Additional information

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